

FarmSmarter

Improving decision-
making in farming

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

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Improving decision-making in farming

Whether for smallholder farms or large-scale agribusinesses, AI is becoming a critical ally in managing resources, improving crop yields and controlling pests.

FarmSmarter's free, easy-to-use smartphone app was originally designed for use in developing countries. It uses AI models to generate advice for farmers, overcoming barriers such as lack of access to specialist equipment or lower levels of literacy. The app supports smallholder farmers by giving them accurate, real-time information and advice, including weather forecasts, field mapping, crop health reports and yield predictions – there's a huge appetite for this type of information.

To do this effectively, efficient machine learning models are essential, yet making sense of the vast number of data points collected is often difficult, such as when sampling images of crops to detect disease. The answer is to combine two techniques: automated deep learning and human-supervised active learning.

"AI has huge potential in the agriculture sector... it has been incredibly rewarding to help FarmSmarter adopt its AI-driven solutions. Seeing the tangible impact reinforces the value of innovation in driving growth for small and medium-sized enterprises."

Dr Po Yang

Senior Lecturer in Large-scale Data Fusion, University of Sheffield

As a BridgeAI Independent Scientific Advisor, Dr Po Yang has worked with the FarmSmarter team to optimise its deep learning models for crop disease recognition, as well as advising on the vital recruitment of AI research engineers to further develop and implement the technology.

“We’ve been very lucky to receive a range of support from BridgeAI and its partner organisations such as the Turing Institute and Hartree Centre, which has helped us get to the point where we are on the verge of being able to launch the full version of our app. Everything we do is geared towards making farming more efficient and sustainable, as well as more profitable and productive for the farmers themselves.”

Rebecca Cole-Coker

Creative Director, FarmSmarter

FarmSmarter is now developing an improved AI model, increasing the scope of its disease identification tool, supporting the next step in its mission to open its services to millions of farmers globally in the next five years.

A roadmap focusing on the viable AI models available to FarmSmarter has been developed in collaboration with the Hartree Centre, and further work on modifying and improving the existing model is ongoing. This has already increased the productivity of FarmSmarter’s R&D, and predicted future impact will be exponential.

The beta version of the app, made possible with BridgeAI support, is now available in the Google Play store, and is being tested by farmers in Nigeria ahead of a planned full rollout in 2025. Meanwhile, an ongoing project with STFC Hartree is exploring how to adapt the app’s AI model for farmers in Europe (including the UK) and South America, where conditions can differ significantly.

Acknowledgement

This case study is published under the **Independent Scientific Advisor (ISA) Turing/BridgeAI** workstream. The ISA programme offers transformative support to SMEs across BridgeAI sectors, enabling them to harness AI for both practical and strategic benefits. This initiative is supported by Innovate UK BridgeAI.

We would like to extend our gratitude to **Paul Coker**, CEO, and **Rebecca Cole-Coker**, Creative Director at FarmSmarter, as well as **Dr. Po Yang**, Independent Scientific Advisor for BridgeAI based at The Alan Turing Institute, and **Megan Yates**, Impact Evidence and Evaluation Manager at Hartree Centre for their significant contributions to the development of this case study.

Special thanks to **Alexandra Araujo Alvarez**, Senior Research Community Manager for BridgeAI, **Dominica D’Arcangelo**, Programme Manager, and **Punita Maisuria**, Project Coordinator, for their leadership and support. We also acknowledge **Stuart Gillespie** for his role as the technical writer for this and other case studies in the programme. Additional thanks go to **Aida Mehonic**, Principal Researcher for Research Applications, and **Shakir Laher** from The Alan Turing Institute for their valuable reviews and feedback.

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